

Kinetic and mechanistic studies on the interaction of DL-penicillamine with di- μ -hydroxobis(bipyridyl)dipalladium(II) ion in aqueous solution

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Abstract : The kinetics of interaction between DL-penicillamine and the title complex is a two-step process in which the first step is ligand dependent, but the second step is ligand independent and is assigned to ring closure. The rate and activation parameters, conductivity studies, IR data were used to deduce a plausible mechanism.

Keywords : Kinetics, interaction, DL-penicillamine, Pd^{II}.

Introduction

Much work have been done on the equilibrium studies of palladium(II) complexes with aliphatic amines^{1,2} and it is of interest to extend this work to the reaction of palladium(II) complexes with heterocycles, such as 2,2'-bipyridine. Aromatic heterocycles can be involved in π - π stacking with purine and pyrimidine bases. This can lead to complex formation with DNA subunits, which is an important target in cancer chemotherapy³.

The μ -hydroxobridged dinuclear complexes act in a different way towards pyrimidine bases compared to mononuclear platinum complexes. As the kinetic and thermodynamic behaviors of both Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} are nearly same, it is expected that the μ -hydroxobridged dinuclear palladium(II) ion will behave similarly to that of platinum(II).

On the basis of recent work, we have focused our research work in our laboratory to study the kinetic and mechanistic interaction of di- μ -hydroxobis(bipyridyl)-dipalladium(II) ion with DL-penicillamine. The goal of our study was (i) to contribute towards the mechanistic understanding of the interaction of related anticancer drug cis-platin with DNA and its constituents⁴. (ii) To investigate the kinetic tuning of such complexes via steric and electronic effects.

Results and discussion

The pK'_1 , pK'_2 and pK'_3 values of DL-penicillamine⁵ are 1.90, 7.88 and 10.58 at 25 °C respectively. So that at pH 7.4 the major species involved in the kinetic process is the neutral form of DL-penicillamine. The pK_1 and pK_2 values for $[Pd(bipy)(H_2O)_2]^{2+}$ as reported in the literature are 4.5 and 9.6 at 25 °C respectively⁶. The equilibrium constant for the dimerisation³, $\log K_{dimer} = 3.12$. From the pK values and from the dimerisation constant it can be shown that at pH 7.4 the percentage of the dimer present in the solution is ~85%. This is supported by the wider literature⁷⁻⁹.

The plots of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$, where A_t and A_∞ are absorbances at time t and after the completion of the reaction, against time were found to be non-linear, being curved at the initial stage and subsequently of constant slope indicates that the reaction is not a single step process, a two step consecutive process may be assumed, where the first step being dependent and the final step is independent of ligand concentration. The method of Weyh and Hamm¹⁰ was adopted to calculate rate constants for two consecutive steps.

The $k_{1(obs)}$ values were obtained are collected in Table 1.

The rate increases with increase in [ligand] before

Table 1. $10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values for different ligand concentrations at different temperatures

[Complex 1] = 2.85×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, pH = 7.4, ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄

10^3 [Ligand] (mol dm ⁻³)	Temperature (°C)			
	30	35	40	45
2.85	1.10	1.35	1.55	2.00
4.27	1.86	2.12	2.68	2.95
5.7	2.40	2.66	3.10	3.45
7.12	2.75	3.10	3.60	3.93
8.55	2.95	3.25	3.81	4.10

reaching a limiting value (Fig. 1), which is probably due to the completion of the outer sphere association complex formation. At this stage, the interchange of the ligands

Fig. 1. Plot of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ versus [DLP] at different temperatures : A = 30, B = 35, C = 40 and D = 45 °C.

from the outer sphere to the inner sphere occurs, i.e. DL-penicillamine attacks one of the Pd^{II} atoms of the dihydroxo-bridged dimer to give the intermediate complex.

Formation of intermediate from the complex 1 can be shown by the following Scheme.

Scheme 1

Based on Scheme 1, a rate expression can be derived for A → B step;

$$d[B]/dt = k_1 K_E [B][DLP]/(1 + K_E[DLP])$$

$$d[B]/dt = K_{1(\text{obs})}[B]_T$$

T stands for total concentration of Pd^{II}. Thus it can be written,

$$k_{1(\text{obs})} = k_1 K_E [DLP]/(1 + K_E [DLP])$$

where k_1 is the rate constant for the formation of intermediate (B) from dihydroxodimer (A). K_E is the outer sphere association equilibrium constant.

The equation can be written as

$$1/k_{1(\text{obs})} = 1/k_1 + 1/k_1 K_E [DLP]$$

A plot of $1/k_{1(\text{obs})}$ versus $1/[\text{ligand}]$ should therefore be linear with an intercept of $1/k_1$ and slope $1/k_1 K_E$.

This was found to be all temperatures studied (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Plot of $1/k_{1(\text{obs})}$ versus $1/[DLP]$ at different temperatures : A = 30, B = 35, C = 40 and D = 45 °C.

The k_1 and K_E values obtained from the intercept and from slope to intercept ratios are given in Table 2.

Table 2. k_1, K_E values		
Temperature (°C)	$10^3 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	K_E (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹)
30	2.35	131
35	3.05	152
40	3.85	175
45	4.24	204

The second step is intramolecular ring closure and is independent of ligand concentration. At a particular temperature the slope of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ versus time plots at different ligand concentrations were found to be constant

in the region where the plots are linear. For different temperatures the k_2 values are obtained directly from the limiting slope and are collected in Table 3 and the average $10^5 k_2$ values are 6.25, 7.51, 8.55 and 9.23 s^{-1} at temperature 30, 35, 40 and 45 °C respectively.

Table 3. $10^5 k_2$ values for different ligand concentrations at different temperatures

[Complex 1] = 2.85×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} , pH = 7.4, ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm^{-3} NaClO₄

10^3 [DLP] (mol dm^{-3})	Temperature (°C)			
	30	35	40	45
2.85	6.23	7.50	8.54	9.22
4.27	6.25	7.53	8.55	9.22
5.7	6.24	7.52	8.56	9.23
7.12	6.27	7.50	8.54	9.23
8.55	6.26	7.51	8.56	9.24

Effects of pH and temperature on the reaction rate :

The reaction was studied at five different pH values. At a fixed concentration of complex, ligand and at constant ionic strength the $10^3 k_{1(obs)}$ values are 3.85, 3.74, 3.63, 3.58 and 3.60 and $10^5 k_2$ values are 6.24, 6.22, 6.24, 6.23 and 6.24 at pHs 5.5, 6.0, 6.5, 7.0 and 7.4 respectively at 30 °C. The $k_{1(obs)}$ values slowly decreases in the lower pH region and remains constant at higher pH region. The change in rate may be explained based on two acid dissociation equilibria of the ligand and the complex.

Firstly, the DL-penicillamine remains in the neutral form from pH 1.9 to 7.88. The effect of pH on rate is due to the change in reactive forms of the reacting complex. Above pH 5.5, >90% of the diaqua complex will be in the hydroxo-aqua form. As the log K_{dimer} value is 3.12 thus it is expected that at pH > 5.0, the hydroxobridged dimer will be the predominant species (~85%) and the

effect of change in pH will be small, observed experimentally. On the other hand the k_2 values are dependent only on the nature of the ligand during bridged formation. So k_2 values are independent on pH. Actually it was found true experimentally under our studied pH region (pH 5.5 to 7.4).

Nevertheless, in the present kinetic runs were followed at a constant pH of 7.4 to avoid complication caused by adding an additional parameter of $[H^+]$ to the rate equation.

Four different temperatures were chosen for study and the results are listed in Table 4. The activation parameters were evaluated from the linear Eyring plots.

Mechanism and conclusion :

Our results indicate that the first step, i.e. the attack by the incoming ligand proceeds by an associative interchange (I_a) mechanism. This proposition is supported by the following observations. First, with an increase in ligand concentration, saturation in the rate is observed. This indicates that is an outer sphere association complex is formed. Second, the low enthalpy of activation and large negative value of entropy of activation strongly suggest that ligand participates in the transition state.

The second step is the intramolecular ring closure which is independent on the incoming ligand concentration. Hence the rate constant (k_2) for this step was found to be actually independent of ligand concentration. The activation parameters for the first and second steps suggest an associative mode of activation for the substitution processes.

It was also found that after completion of the reaction, both the pH and conductance of the resulting solution had increased, which might be due to loss of one of the bridging OH groups, consequently ring closure occurs through sulphur bridging.

Table 4. Thermodynamic and activation parameters for substitution of [Complex 1] by various ligands in aqueous medium, pH = 7.4

Ligand	ΔH_1^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS_1^\ddagger (J K^{-1} mol^{-1})	ΔH^0 (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS^0 (J K^{-1} mol^{-1})	ΔH_2^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS_2^\ddagger (J K^{-1} mol^{-1})	Ref
DL-Methionine	46.0 ± 1.5	-101 ± 5			*	*	11
Thiosemicarbazide	50.4 ± 1.9	-105 ± 6			*	*	12
L-Cysteine	33.6 ± 1.5	-134 ± 5			*	*	13
DL-Penicillamine	30.29 ± 1	-195 ± 5	22.86 ± 1.4	115 ± 3	16 ± 1.5	-272 ± 6	This work

* Previous studies indicated a single step reaction, but we have found a two-step reaction for the current system.

Experimental

[Pd(bipy)Cl₂] (bipy = 2,2'-bipyridine) was prepared by literature methods^{14,15}. The diaqua complex [Pd(bipy)(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₂ was prepared by the method of Hay and Basak¹⁶ by stirring the chloro complex with two mole equivalents of AgClO₄ followed by keeping overnight (with careful protection from light). The precipitated AgCl was removed by filtration and the filtrate was made up to the requisite volume in a standard flask. The reactant complex di- μ -hydroxobis(bipyridyl)dipalladium(II) ion (complex 1) was obtained *in situ* by adjusting the pH to 7.4 with NaOH/HClO₄. The reaction product of DL-penicillamine (DLP) and complex 1 was prepared by mixing the reactants in different ratios namely 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 5 and 1 : 10 and keeping at 50 °C for 24 h. The absorption spectra of these mixtures all exhibited the same λ_{\max} with nearly identical intensities.

The composition of the product was determined by Job's method of continuous variation which indicates a 2 : 1 metal ligand ratio.

Complex and the ligand were mixed in 2 : 1 molar ratio at pH 7.4 and a yellow product was obtained. The IR spectra of the yellow product in the KBr disc shows strong bands at 3628–3552, 3417, 3236, 1637–1617, 1430, 1089, 627 and 472 cm⁻¹. Bands appear at 1637–1617 cm⁻¹ due to asymmetric N–H out of plane bending of amino acid. At the same time, a broad spectrum appears at 1620–1590 cm⁻¹ due to overlapping of symmetric stretching of N–H and COO⁻, indicating that the -COOH group is not involved in bonding. No broad spectrum is appear at 3200–3150 cm⁻¹, which indicate that -NH₂ group is not involve in the binding with Pd^{II} in the product complex. The band at 1430 cm⁻¹ is assigned to symmetric stretching of COO⁻¹⁷. A sharp peak at 472 cm⁻¹ appears due to Pd^{II}-S-Pd^{II} stretching frequency¹⁸. The broad strong band appears at 1089 and 627 cm⁻¹ is due to formation of perchlorate salt of the complex. A broad peak is observed at 3628–3552 cm⁻¹ for Pd^{II} metal-metal bridged O–H str. frequency, which is not correspond to the OH group of -COOH of DL-penicillamine because it remain as carboxylate (COO⁻) at pH 7.4 and again a sharp band at 3236 cm⁻¹ due to N–H str. frequency. The IR spectrum suggests that the final product is DL-penicillamine's sulphur coordinated chelate and sulphur behaves as bridging ligand with both the Pd^{II} bridged species.

Conductance measurements also help us to identify the product. During the course of the reaction there is release of OH⁻ ion, as shown by increase in conductance and pH. This is consistent with substitution of OH⁻ by DLP.

The pH of the solution was adjusted by adding NaOH/HClO₄, and the pH measurements were made with a Sartorius digital pH meter (model PB11) with an accuracy of ± 0.01 units. Doubly distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The reactions were carried out at constant ionic strength (0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄).

Spectroscopic measurements were made with a Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UV-2101). IR spectra (KBr disc, 4000–300 cm⁻¹) were measured on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR RX1 spectrophotometer. Conductance measurements were carried out in a Systronics conductivity meter (Model 308), where the cell constant was calibrated with 0.01 M KCl solution and water used as solvent.

The kinetic studies were done on a Shimadzu UV 2101 PC spectrophotometer attached to a thermoelectric cell temperature controller (Model Shimadzu TB 85 thermobath, accuracy ± 0.1 °C). The development of a characteristic peak of the product complex (complex 2) at 278 nm was monitored with time at different fixed temperatures. The conventional mixing technique was followed and a pseudo-first order conditions were employed throughout.

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